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ABSTRACT BOOK

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**30TH EAA ANNUAL MEETING
ROME, ITALY
28TH - 31ST AUGUST 2024**

EAA 2024 mobile app

30th EAA Annual Meeting (Rome, Italy 2024) - Abstract Book
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6 A LOOK AT THE MORPHOTYOLOGY OF COPPER AGE BETILES IN IBERIA. ON THE LOS MILLARES ASSEMBLAGES

Dorado-Alejos, Alberto (Lab. of Archaeometry, Department of Prehistory and Archaeology, University of Granada) - Quero Díaz, Ada (Lab. of Archaeometry, Department of Prehistory and Archaeology, University of Granada) - Núñez Caravaca, Helena Adriana (Lab. of Archaeometry, Department of Prehistory and Archaeology, University of Granada) - Pérez l'Huillier, Daniel (Lab. of Archaeometry, Department of Prehistory and Archaeology, University of Granada) - Maldonado Ruiz, Alexis (University of Santiago de Compostela | Visiting Research Fellow, Leiden University.) - Castillo Gallego, Francisco Javier (Department of Prehistory and Archaeology, University of Granada) - Pinillos de la Granja, Paula (Department of Prehistory and Archaeology, University of Granada) - Basso Rial, Ricardo (University Institute of Research in Archaeology and Heritage, University of Alicante | Visiting Research Fellow Department of Prehistory and Archaeology, University of Granada) - García Martínez, Victoria (Department of Prehistory and Archaeology, University of Granada) - Cámara Serrano, Juan Antonio (Department of Prehistory and Archaeology, University of Granada)

Anthropomorphic figures called “betilos” present a large distribution in Iberia, but variations in shape and decoration can be traced depending on the different societies that produce them. In any case, their presence in necropolis areas allows us to relate these artefacts to specific funerary and symbolic practices, which must have constituted a certain ‘Iberian norm’ as they were found in different areas. In this way, their production was probably linked to common beliefs that we can try to decipher by studying their production processes, taking into account that both concrete shapes and specific raw material could be intrinsically linked to the territories in which they were produced and, usually, used. The aim of the present study is the morphometric characterisation -based on the analysis of their shapes and sizes- of these symbolic items in order to identify the formal patterns that define the “betilos” in their large area of distribution in Southern Iberia during the Copper Age. For this aim items from Los Millares necropolis -which is the main focus of this study as it includes some analytical data-, Hidalgo Dolmen, Palacio Megalithic Complex, Dolmen de Dombate, Mina de Parxubeira and A Cova da Moura are analysed. It's supposed that formal features of these items can provide a chance for the identification of large cultural groups that could constitute the areas of influence of relevant sites such as Valencina de la Concepción, Los Millares or Zambujal, for example. The results allow us to point out, for the moment, the existence of three large groupings that help to decipher differential technical knowledge but with shared symbolic patterns, as shown by the use of these “betilos” at the entrance of the corridors. The proposed morphotypological approach is intended to be a useful tool for the identification, recording and interpretation of new “betilos”.

7 THE COASTAL MEGALITH SITE OF PIETRA TARA, PALERMO. THE CULT SYSTEM OF THE UPPER ZONE. FIRST ANALYSIS OF THE ACROPOLIS

Mercadante, Francesca (Studio GeoArchPa Palermo) - Cabrero Correo, Carolina (Department of Prehistory and Archaeology, University of Granada)

The coastal megalith site of Pietra Tara is located on the northernmost side of western Sicily, on Monte Gallo, Palermo, in front of the Tyrrhenian Sea. It appears to be the only known site in Sicily with megalithic/cyclopean constructions, still intact, with landslide carbonate blocks, adapted to menhirs. To facilitate the study, the area was indicated in two portions: Lower Zone, from the coastline up to 60 meters above sea level, and Upper Zone, from 60 meters above sea level, up to under the cliff of Monte. The funerary architecture is widespread and connected with the structures of the entire site, mainly with the intramural dolmen hypogea. Starting from the altitude mt. 50 above sea level the slope becomes steep (30-40% slope), has some hilltops, with accumulation of stone material along the steep slopes. In July 2023, a lidar drone flight was carried out over the entire area, which highlighted a small acropolis in the Upper Zone with megalithic constructions, with partially ruined megaliths and mounds. The acropolis has architectural spatial characteristics different from the underlying Zone B, it has a polygonal closure made up of cyclopean blocks, with double-faced walls, with a first ovoid shed environment leaning against the ZA.1 megalith. Furthermore, at higher altitudes there are two pseudo-rectangular rooms cutting into a thick wall. In the first instance it could be argued that we are in the presence of a secluded area, whose architectural system, formed by the two megaliths, (ZA.2 and ZA.3) appears as the entrance to a cult/funerary place with the presence of mounds, in which the Megalith ZA.2 takes on the condition of an “anthropomorphic Monolith”, as a reference to the female Goddess, while the second ZA.3, behind it, acts as a funerary hypogeum. The cult/funerary system is flanked by terraces with shed structures

643 THE EXPERIENCE OF STONE II: SCULPTING COMPARATIVE PHENOMENOLOGIES

Session theme: 4. Persisting with Change: Theory and Archaeological Scrutiny

Session organisers: Smith, Christina (Durham University) - D'Alisera, Alexander (Boston College)

Session format: Regular session

The Experience of Stone hits Rome! Building upon the success of last year's all-day panel, this session offers explorations into the phenomenology of stone sculpture and monuments, stone artefacts, stone buildings, and natural landscapes of stone. In the words of Maurice Merleau-Ponty, 'The body is our general medium for having a world.' Centred on EAA 2024's theme 'persisting with change', this session explores how stone constructs (and is mediated by) a viewer's sensorial experience. Phenomenology offers a way for thinking about the affective presence of stone, stone monuments, and natural stonescapes, and proves particularly important for periods and places where the textual record is scant.

We invite scholars of all time periods, geographies, and disciplines—but especially archaeologists, historians, and art historians working from the prehistoric to medieval periods—to contribute papers exploring comparative phenomenologies of stone. Papers that examine geographically or temporally cross-border case-studies are particularly welcome. Possible subjects include, but are not limited to: comparative stonescapes; reuse of hewn or sculptured stone; epigraphy through changing viewership; sculpting memory; textual references to the experience of stone; stone and empire; agentive stone; the application of viewsheds in spatial analysis; a theology of stone; multi-media stone monuments; and, landscape archaeology. As with last year's panel, this session aims to offer a forum through which history, archaeology, and other disciplines may continue to develop further scholarly discourse and collaboration.

ABSTRACTS

1 PERSISTENCE OR CHANGE? THE USE OF STONE IN THE ROOFING SYSTEMS OF ROMANESQUE CHURCHES OF NORTHERN ITALY (11TH-12TH CENTURIES)

Passuello, Angelo (Marie Skłodowska-Curie Postdoctoral Fellow - University of Cyprus (Archaeological Research Unit))

Some structural systems assumed a fundamental importance in the formulation of the architectural language of sacred space in the Middle Ages. Chief among them was the emergence of varied roofing solutions that decisively conditioned the internal spatiality and also assumed a key role in shaping the external form of ecclesiastical buildings, since the entire design would be affected by the shape that the roof was meant to have.

This paper will present the first results of the Cataloguing Medieval Roofs (CaMeRoofs) project, funded by the European Commission under the Marie Skłodowska-Curie Actions, which I am carrying out at the Archaeological Research Unit of the University of Cyprus.

According to a common view, Romanesque architecture drew inspiration from the great Roman basilicas by making stone roofs and giving up the wooden ceilings of early Christian origin. The experience of stone, therefore, would be quintessential for the development of the spatial concept typical of Romanesque churches. Nevertheless, was this truly the case?

This paper, in line with the conference's main theme, “Persisting with Change”, will consider some examples of Northern Italian churches (regions of Veneto, Lombardy, Piedmont, Emilia Romagna) with a view to examining more closely whether it was really the use of stone vaults that acted as a catalyst for change in Romanesque design and construction.

In order to broach this and related questions, the project in question employs an archaeological (and not just an architectural-historical) approach to the study of medieval roofing systems. The aim is to attempt an interpretation of the structural relationship between the churches' roofing and the load-bearing walls, highlighting any discontinuities and design or phase changes (stratigraphic analysis), to identify restorations and modifications, and analyze in detail the construction technologies applied to the stone vaulting.

2 PEARLY STARS, CELESTIAL REFLECTIONS, AND PENDENT VERSE: THE FOUNTAIN OF THE LIONS IN THE GARDEN OF BLISS

Cottignoli, Emilia (Stanford University)

This study explores the stone architecture of the Fountain of the Lions in the Garden of Bliss and its phenomenological, material flux from solid stone to running water. Converging as a center of liquidity, the basin at the center of the fountain becomes a glittering eye in this liquid waterscape as the highest point in reflection of the sky, mirroring the clouds, sun, and moon in its vessel, ingathering the distant sky in the form of reflection. Characterized by the slippage